

Trichomoniasis Detection Rate Among Female Patients Consulting Different Clinics in Duhok City, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Helan Saman Jameel

M.Sc., Department of anesthesia science, College of health science, University of Duhok, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Bayram Dawod Ahmed

Ph.D., Department of anesthesia science, college of health science, university of Duhok, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Bland Husamuldeen Abdullah (Ph.D)

Department of medical laboratory science, college of health science, university of Duhok, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Majeed Hussein Mustafa

FIBMS, Department of anesthesia science, college of health science, university of Duhok, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Reaber Haji Qadir

FIBMS, Department of anesthesia science, college of health science, university of Duhok, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

More Information

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Abstract

Background: Trichomoniasis is a highly prevalent sexually transmitted infection which leads to several public health risks such as urethritis, vaginitis, eventually abortion and sterility and it has been associated with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV).

Aim of the study: The current cross-sectional study was conducted to measure the rate of Trichomoniasis among female patients consulting different clinics based on direct examination of vaginal swabs, urine samples and cervical discharges specimens.

Materials and method: A total of 276 specimens (106 vaginal, 169 urine and 9 cervical) were collected from females aged 18 -45 years consulting four clinics from November, 2022 to May, 2023. The desired patient information was obtained through a designed questionnaire sheet. All specimens processed and examined by direct microscopy following standard protocols. Results were analyzed statistically by Chi-square test and a p value ≥ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The overall rate of positivity was 9.78% (27 out of 276). The detection rates by examining vaginal swab wet mount, urine wet mount and cervical wet mount methods were 14.15% (15 out of 106), 6.21% (10 out of 161) and 22.22% (2 out of 9) respectively. There were almost no significant differences between the infection and socio-demographic variables and methods used.

Conclusion: The direct microscopy of vaginal swab or urine specimens still has a useful ability to discover positive cases. In order to increase positivity rates additional more sensitive diagnostic techniques such as regular polymerase chain reaction methods for suspected cases are recommended.

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Introduction

Trichomonas vaginalis is considered one of the most common curable sexually transmitted infections and the majority of women who have the infection are

asymptomatic, but occasionally they experience modest symptoms such as dysuria, unusual vaginal discharge, itching, irritation, and abdominal pain [1]. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated 156

million cases in 2016 [2]. The disease results in low birthweight and preterm deliveries and other health issues [3]. *Trichomoniasis* causes several adverse health problems such as preterm birth and a low birth-weight baby [4]. Untreated *T. vaginalis* infections can result in pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) and adverse birth outcomes [5]. The parasite poses a public health challenge in addition to being a personal one because it may not show symptoms at all. Poor sexual behaviors, such as having several partners, high socioeconomic level, and HIV and Hepatitis B virus infections are among the at-risk groups contributing to the rising incidence of vaginal trichomonas [6]. The prevalence of *T. vaginalis* may vary depending on sociocultural variables, individual health status, geography, and sex [7]. Nonspecific symptomatology and a lack of routine testing are further factors influencing this problem [8]. There have been reports of *Trichomonas vaginalis* co-infections with *Chlamydia trachomatis* and/or *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* in women, and symptoms from these infections can coexist [9]. The inclusion of *T. vaginalis* testing in alongside *C. trachomatis*/*N. gonorrhoeae* testing is anticipated to significantly improve case detection in groups with high levels of STI exposure [10]. Direct microscopic analysis of a wet vaginal swab

and or a urine examination is the most widely used conventional method in the world for diagnosing a *T. vaginalis* infection. However, this method's sensitivity is less than 60%, it takes expertise and the hands of a skilled observer, and it is only helpful for women who are symptomatic [11].

This study was conducted to assess the prevalence of *T. vaginalis*, its associated risk factors and evaluating its different diagnostic methods using urine and vaginal swabs from female patients by using the direct wet-mounts microscopy.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

In this cross-sectional study a total of 276 samples of vaginal swab and urine specimens were collected from different patients attending different Private Gynecological Clinics in Duhok, Kurdistan Region. The sample collection was started from November 2022 to May 2023. All patients who had been on antiprotozoal for the past 2 weeks were excluded from the study. A designed questionnaire was also used to acquire related socio-demographic and clinical data from each female including age, residency, occupation, main symptoms and the clinic they visited as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Variables and Sociodemographic Characteristic of Samples and Participants

S. N	Characteristics	S. N	Variables	No. and (%)
1	Age groups	1	18-21	27
		2	22-25	42
		3	26-29	53
		4	30-33	37
		5	34-37	46
		6	38-41	33
		7	42-45	23
		8	≥45 Years	15
2	Residency	1	Urban	164
		2	Rural	112
3	Occupation	1	Housewives	169
		2	Employees	91
		3	Students	16
4	Symptoms	1	Fever	32
		2	Sweating	13
		3	Itching	81
		4	Dysuria	9
		5	Burning sensation	58
		6	Back pain	44
		7	Abdominal pain	39
5	Visited clinic	1	Family planning clinic	31
		2	Obstetric/Genecology clinic	73
		3	Sexually transmitted infection clinic	144
		4	Family planning clinic/STI clinic	28

Sample Collection and Laboratory Diagnosis

The gynecologists obtained vaginal and cervical swabs using sterile cotton swab sticks from the posterior fornix and cervix of the vagina followed by immediately soaking into transport medium tubes then kept in an ice pack box until processing .Later, wet mount slide smears of the samples were prepared using a regular saline drop in order to identify viable *T. vaginalis* trophozoites and examined immediately under a light microscope using a light microscope with a 10X low power objective lens and 40X high power objective lens to look for motile trichomonad trophozoites , Three slides from each specimen were prepared and examined in order to increase the chances of demonstrating the parasite. All specimens containing one or more Trichomonas vaginalis trophozoites were considered positive while, any sample not contain any trophozoites was considered negative for parasites. Regarding urine samples an approximately 20–40 ml of each sample was collected for examination according to Adjei *et al.* method [12]. The samples were properly

mixed then an aliquot of 10 ml was centrifuged for 5 minutes at 2000 rpm. Finally, a drop of sediment was examined under the microscope to look for parasite trophozoites.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis is performed using Microsoft Excel 2016 to find the association between sociodemographic and clinical characteristics and *T. vaginalis* infection, Chi-square was applied for determination of variances and a p value ≥ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethics Approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the scientific committee of the College of Health Sciences of University of Duhok as well as a written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Results

The overall detection rate was 9.82% (27 out of 276), the detection rates between age groups were variable but there were no statically significant differences (*P*= 0.2) between different age groups as shown in table 2.

Table 2: The Distribution of Trichomonas Vaginalis According to Age Groups

Age group/Years	Total no. examined	No. (%) of Pos.	No. (%) of Neg.	Chi2 values	P value
18-21	27	4(14.81%)	23(85.19%)	10.11713	P = 0.2
22-25	42	2(4.76%)	40(95.24%)		
26-29	53	5(9.43%)	48(90.57%)		
30-33	37	8(21.62%)	29(78.38%)		
34-37	46	3(6.52%)	43(93.43%)		
38-41	33	2(6.06%)	31(93.94%)		
42-45	23	2(8.70%)	21(91.30%)		
≥45 Years	15	1(6.67%)	14(93.33%)		
Total	276	27(9.78%)	249(90.22%)		

Although there were different detection rates among patients with different presenting symptoms such as it was among those with burning sensation 46.55%,

itching 33.33%, genital discharge 26.87% and with back pain 29.55% respectively but there were no statically differences (p value 0.3) as seen in table 3.

Table 3: Detection Rate According to the Dominant Signs and Symptoms

S.N	Dominant symptom	Number Examined	No. (%) of Positive	Chi2 value	P value
1	Fever	32	8(25%)	6.269	0.3
2	Sweating	13	2(15.38%)		
3	Itching	81	27(33.33%)		
4	Dysuria	9	1(11.11%)		
5	Burning sensation	58	27(46.55%)		
6	Back pain	44	13(29.55%)		
7	Abdominal pain	39	5(12.82%)		
		276			

Regarding the residency of patients and positivity rates the results showed no statistical differences (P value

0.2) between both rural and urban people as seen in table 4.

Table 4: Positivity Detection Rate According to Residency

Residency	Total no. examined	No. (%) of Pos.	No. (%) of Neg.	Chi2 values	P ≤ 0.05
Urban	164	19(11.59%)	145(88.41%)	1.23287	P = 0.2
Rural	112	8(7.14%)	104(92.86%)		
Total	276	27(9.78%)	249(90.22%)		

Concerning the occupation, the results showed no significant differences among different occupations (P value 0.5) since a highest number of positive cases seen

among housewives 70.41% (19 out of 169) followed by students 12.50% (2 out of 16) and lastly employees 6.59% (6 out of 91) as shown in table 5.

Table 5: The Distribution of Trichomonas Vaginalis among Women According to Occupation

Occupation	Total no. examined	No. (%) of Pos.	No. (%) of Neg.	Chi2 values	P≤0.05
Housewives	169	19(70.41%)	150(88.76%)	1.32599	P = 0.5
Employees	91	6(6.59%)	85(93.41%)		
Students	16	2(12.50%)	14(87.50%)		
Total	276	27(9.78%)	249(90.22%)		

Different positivity rates of T. vaginalis infection stratified by type of specimen and test methods are seen in table 6 such as; by using vaginal swab wet mount examination method it was 14.15% (15 out of

106) followed by urine wet mount method 6.21% (10 out of 161), and lastly cervical wet mount method 22.22% (2 out of 9), the differences were not significant and p value was 0.08.

Table 6: Frequency of Trichomonas Vaginalis Trophozoites According to Sample Type and Laboratory Test Method Used for Detecting Trichomoniasis

Test methods	Total no. examined	Pos. (%)	Neg. (%)	Chi2 values	P≤0.05
Vaginal sample (HVS) wet mount	106	15(14.15%)	91(85.84%)	4.9526005	P= 0.08
Urine wet mount	161	10(6.21%)	151(93.78%)		
Cervical discharge/Wet mount	9	2(22.22%)	7(77.77%)		
Total	276	27(9.78%)	249(90.22%)		

As seen in table 7, the current study showed no statistically differences (P value 0.4) between clinic visited while most of positive cases were among who visited STI clinic 16 out of 27 the who visited gynecology

clinic (6 out of 27), followed by family planning / STI clinic (4 out of 27) and the least was among who visited family planning clinic (1 out of 27).

Table 7: The Distribution of Trichomonas Vaginalis According to Visited Clinic

Special clinics names	Total no. examined	No. (%) of Pos. of specimens	No. (%) of Neg. of specimens	Chi2 values	*P≤0.05
Family planning clinic	31	1(3.23%)	30(96.77%)	2.64356	P= 0.4
Obstetric/Genecology clinic	73	6(8.22%)	67(91.78%)		
STI clinic	144	16(11.11%)	128(88.89%)		
Family planning clinic/STI clinic	28	4(14.29%)	24(85.71%)		
Total	276	27(9.78%)	249(90.22%)		

Discussion

The flagellated protozoan Trichomonas vaginalis is mainly found in the human urogenital tract and is the

cause of trichomoniasis [13]. The low detection rate of Trichomonas infections in Duhok City may be attributed to the fact that the majority of cases show no

symptoms at all, making them asymptomatic carriers [14]. Due of its recent correlation with disparate gynecological and obstetric outcomes, infertility, and HIV, routine hurdles towards the diagnosis of trichomoniasis have become more significant [15].

This low infection incidence is most likely the result of routine laboratory testing processes that may have made the issue worse in addition to general misunderstanding. The results of this investigation are almost as reliable as those of a study conducted in Iran by Alikhani et al. [16].

Moreover, Field et al. [17] found urinary *T. vaginalis* in the UK, among sexually experienced women between the ages of 16 and 44. Nevertheless, a study conducted by Al-Saeed et al. [18] utilizing the culture-based detection method revealed a frequency of 5.4% in the Iraqi province of Duhok. As well, in a Ghanaian study by Asmah et al. [19] 64 out of 150 samples were positive for *T. vaginalis*, since Asmah et al. used the (PCR) technology, but we did not.

Geographical disparities could also have a role in the variations in prevalence rates, as the current investigation was carried out in the heart of Duhok City. Furthermore, urogenital trichomonosis prevalence was reported to be 3.2% in a Burkina Faso study conducted by Sangare et al. [20].

T. vaginalis diagnostic revealed that wet mount microscopy could only detect 27 (9.78%) *T. vaginalis* positives, in accordance with the effectiveness of laboratory tests for detecting trichomoniasis. These detection rates are more appropriate for the prevalent underdiagnosis and underestimate of the vaginalis issue. Further studies have assessed the potential use of urine specimens in the hunt for less intrusive human samples for the identification of *T. vaginalis*.

On the other hand, Duhok city has a wealth of skilled microscopy that may be readily customized in microbiology labs for a variety of everyday tasks. For the routine diagnosis of parasites in STI in several Kurdistan Regions and Duhok City, it continues to be the conformist detection method. The findings, however, point to a possible lack of ability for wet mount microscopy to distinguish between patients who have the disease and those who do not in our subgroup sample .

This result contrasts with findings conducted in Ghana by Adjei et al. [13] and India by Patil et al. [21]. This study also found that, with the exception of results that indicated a statistically significant difference (P value 0.01) in relation to sample color, there was no statistically significant correlation between sociodemographic factors and some clinical characteristics associated with trichomoniasis. The results similarly support a study by Adjei et al. [13], which found that, with the exception of individuals presenting with abdominal pain ($p = 0.01$), there was no

significant association between demographic and clinical variables and *T. vaginalis* infection .

The age group of 30 to 33 years old had the highest infection rate (21.62%) among the individuals in this study. The findings support the idea that sexually active people are more likely to be in the highest age category, which is a reasonable explanation for the observed patterns. WHO, [22] trichomoniasis is a sensitive indicator of high-risk sexual conduct. The results also reflect study in Iran by Nazari et al. [23].

The study conducted by Fernando et al. [24] in Sri Lanka, there was no statistically significant association found between *T. vaginalis* infection and clinical or demographic features. However, significant associations with age, ethnicity, and education were discovered by Helms et al. [25].

A statistically significant association (P value 0.01) was found between the patient's positive for trichomoniasis and the presence of different colors of samples where the most common color was greenish followed by white, yellow and bloody. This finding showed in agreement with Alikhani et al. [16] and in difference with Adjai et al. [13].

The microscopic wet mount method performed best for the vaginal sample compared to the urine sample. Conversely, the discrepancy can be related to the possible presence of not viable *T. vaginalis* in the cultures from the samples [26]. The study is limited by the fact that we did not undertake either the more sensitive polymerase chain reaction (PCR) approach or the ELISA, which may have lowered the overall prevalence of the infection .

Therefore, it is imperative that women, particularly those living in less affluent neighborhoods, camps, and rural regions, get education about the importance of personal hygiene and how to properly clean their intimate areas (vagina and anus).With the implementation of the syndromic treatment approach for genital diseases in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, this study enabled us to update the epidemiology of urogenital trichomoniasis in the Duhok area.

Conclusions

Women are prone to *T. vaginalis* infection in Duhok region; also, there is a noteworthy association among some of clinical and demographic traits and trichomoniasis. Therefore, we advise raising females' knowledge of their health and encouraging them to have regular checkups, particularly if they have vaginal discharge, burning, itching, or abdominal pain. When a prompt diagnosis is necessary, the wet mount or culture method is somewhat necessary.

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